

History Taking and Diagnosis of Autism Spectrum Disorder: A Case Study

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>Autism spectrum disorder is considered in broad neurodevelopmental disorder, experience in roughly 1 in 68 children globally (Autism and Developmental Disabilities Monitoring Network Surveillance, 2014). The current paper examined children with autism through the acute illness of child may look challenge to identify in etiological factors, diagnosis and management that can detrimental impact on child life. The complexities stem in great determine from the vital the syndrome's characteristics. Exclusively, Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is differentiated by impairment in reciprocal social interactions, communication skills, and repetitive, restricted, and stereotyped prototypes of interests and behavior (American Psychiatric Association, 2013, Llaneza, DeLuke, Batista, Crawley, Christodulu, & Frye, 2010). Moreover, ASD is frequently escorted and differentiated by core diagnostic features as impairments in cognitive and attention deficit, adaptive functioning, self-injurious behavior or aggression, and sensory processing disorder (Schaaf, Toth-Cohen, Johnson, Outten, & Benevides, 2011). Single case study technique was used based on experimental design. The Present case study the manifestations of this autism features on her psychological functioning and personality employing a structured clinical interview and inclusively psychological battery such as the Gallium Autism Rating Scale (GARS-2), the Standard Progressive Matrices, Adaptive Behavior Scale (ABS) and the House Tree Person (HTP). These examinations were helpful in formulating a diagnosis and a treatment plan. She fulfilled diagnostic criteria for Autism spectrum disorder. This combination of projective and non-projective tests may be helpful in establishing sufficient diagnosis and comprehend the psychological and behavioral problems of child autism cases in parallel cases. The study also proposes that Applied Behavioral Analysis (ABA), Speech Therapy, Play Therapy, and Picture Exchange Communication System (PECS) are helpful therapeutic techniques for children with autistic.</i></p>
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Introduction

Ms. XY is 6 year and 8 month old girl, She belongs to the middle socio economic status family. She is the first born child and has two younger brothers. She is studying in level one. Her mother brings client to National Institute of Rehabilitation Medicine (NIRM). She was under supervision by psychiatrist, he referred her for a understand psychological assessment after her mother different problems that was observed at school from last six-month period. She came with the complaints of marked impairment in communication, echolalia, slurred language, poor eye contact, social isolation. In addition, her emotional expressions do not meet with each other. She focuses on the parts of the objects than to the whole object. She has significant problems developing nonverbal communication skills, such as eye-contact, facial expressions, and body posture. She fails to establish friendships with children of the same age. She has lack of interest in sharing enjoyment, interests, or achievements with other people. She has lack of empathy she does not understands the others feelings, happiness and sorrows. She learnt speaking delayed. She has Problems in taking steps to start a conversation. She has difficulties in continuing a conversation after it has begun. She has a stereotyped and repetitive use of language. She often repeats over and over phrases which she has heard previously (echolalia). She has limited interests in the play activities.

Particularly, in the initial interview, Ms. XY was unable to maintain eye-contact with the examiner and gazed continuously at her friend sitting a bit away. It was difficult to build rapport with the client. The client felt uncomfortable. She had stereotyped movements. The client did not laugh with her friend. Her emotions did not match her behavior. She repeatedly said, she wants to go to the teacher like "mujhe teacher k pass janahae". The client was quite lazy and slept excessively for 4 or more months as compare to the normal children when she was born. She was stubborn and the client repeated sentences like "mujhe teacher k pas janahae".

Personal history

Pre-natal and Peri-natal history

According to the client's mother she had no pre and postnatal complications. she had normal delivery and the client was a healthy normal baby. She covered all developmental milestones age appropriately.

Postnatal history

The client's birth weight was normal. The client received proper vaccination. The client did not achieve her developmental milestones at appropriate age but she started sitting at the age of 4. The client was breast fed for four months and then later was bottle fed. The client did not speak even a single word before age 4 and then she started speaking ammi and abbu at 2 ½ years. She started speaking at the age of 5 years. He used to repeat the same word for several times and tried to imitate other's language. She had very poor eye contact. She was not defensive and can't protect himself. And whenever and wherever he saw fans; she stopped there and started to speak about fan. The client had sleeping problem and eating problem. She was toilet trained at the age of four years.

School history

The client was admitted in the school recently in the age of 6 and ½. Before that the child was not admitted in the school. She was admitted in the school in the march' 2011. In the initial days the child was unable to read and write. According to the mother the client now is able to read two letters like "A, B" and she is improving.

Peer relationship

My client's mother did not leave her to play with the other children because the client beat the children. So the client was preferably kept at home. In order to avoid client's aggression towards the other children. The client was kept aloof from the other child. She pinched and slapped the children. She tried to nudge the children. But now after getting therapies the client's relationships are improving. The client is left to play and learn with her younger brother.

Family History

Both parents of the client are helping, caring and supportive and provide her with full attention and care. My client is not only the child that who is autistic but her 2 year brother is also showing the autistic features. The client's parents are also concerned about their two year old son. But in the parents of the client no such case has been reported yet. My client is the first in her family having autism.

Relationship with mother

The client has healthy relation with her mother as she insisted to stay with her mother. The client's mother cares for her client and loves. She is quite concerned about the problems of her child as she brought her child to the center for getting cure and trained. The client's mother is supportive to the client. The mother helped the client in daily life and fulfilled her biological needs in a nice manner.

Relationship with father

The client has healthy and friendly relationship with her father. Father of the client has provided her with a lot of attention and care and the client is strongly attached with her father. Every evening, she goes in park with her father. she is very much close to her father and considers her father as a friend. He used to play with her father.

Relationship with the siblings

The client has no more good relationship with her brothers. Mother of the client pays more attention to the younger child than to the Client. That's why Client did not like her brothers. Her mother did not leave her daughter alone. She was afraid that client might not beat or pinch him. According to the mother the client shows little anger or tantrums than before. The mother now leaves Client to play with her middle child. Client has learnt a lot of good behavior from her brothers. She learnt how to brush and how to wear clothes on her own.

Family History of Medical or Psychiatric Illness

The client's parents are healthy physically and mentally. According to her mother her younger brother who is 2 years old has also the autistic features which may make him vulnerable to the autism. Before the client there has not been any autistic case witnessed in the family. The parents are sound minded, mentally healthy and normal.

Medical History

According to the client's mother, the client was a delayed-child as she had learnt to sit late and learnt to walk late. Spoke in the age of 4 only two words and at the age of 5 the client spoke completely. This indicates that the client had serious problems in the childhood. She only complained of delayed speech and delayed walking of the client. The client's mouth salivated all the time when she was too young. She had constipation for a longer period of time.

Pre-morbid Personality

Client has never lived a healthy life. She has been suffering from the day. she was born. Recently the client has been admitted in the step-to-learn for getting further training and cure.

Developmental History

According to the client's mother the client was born normally. The client spoke two or three words at the age of 4 and after the 5 years of age the client started speaking full sentences. The client was quite lazy and slept for 4 or more months as compare to the normal children. The client was made sit with the help of the pillows by her mother. And the client was even delayed in walking. She started walking after 2 ½ years. The client behaved in an odd way did not even tell the mother for going to washroom and pissed out in the pent. Client had two brothers. The client was left on her own will to do her works by herself. The client simulated a lot of good behavior from her brother, like how to brush her teethes and how to clean herself?

Additionally to a comprehensive psychiatric assessment, numerous psychological tests has been used todetermine IQ level (Colored Progressive Matrices [CPM]), autism (Gallium Autism Rating Scale [GARS]), cognitive, social, and interpersonal functioning (Adaptive Behavior Scale [ABS]), and (Human person Tree [HTP]). Psychiatrist evaluation demonstrated that she had not symptoms of attention deficient hyper activity disorder (ADHD), Conduct disorder, (CD), Intellectual disability (ID), and learning disorder (LD).the rationale for employing these instruments are explained infollowing section.Keeping in view the symptoms and the problems indicated in the behavior of the client as well as reported by the mother and significant others, following scales were administered for the assessment of the client to have a clear idea of the problem.

Standard Progressive Matrices (SPM). Standard progressive Matrices (SPM:Raven, 1960; Raven, & Raven, 1998) was employed toevaluate intellectual ability of individual. It comprised on 36-items.For these dimension high scores indicate high intelligent of that particular dimension and low score reveals that low intelligent in particular dimension and to ask participant respond rate on specified pictures.

HouseTreePerson. (HTP; John Buck (1948)& Emmanuel Hammer (1958), isused to measure personality for children and adults. The client is simply instructed to make a freehand drawing of a house, a tree, and a person. It is nonverbal and almost entirely unstructured; the medium of expression is the freehand, pencil drawings of a house, tree, and person (Buck 1966).

Gallium Autism Rating Scale(GARS-2; Billingsley, 1995) was used to evaluateautism spectrum disorders for children and adults. It comprised of42-items that need parents of autistic children to rate their level of concord on a scale of 0 (*never observed*) to 3 (*frequently observed*).High scores reflect greater prevalence of autistic feature and low scores reveallower autistic prevalence.

Adaptive Behavior Scale(ABS; Lambert, Nihira, & Leland, 1993)is employed to evaluate stereotyped behaviors, communication problems, and social interaction for children and adults.This scale comprise of 25 items having twomain domains. First part of scale isdesigned to assess independence, coping skills and responsibility. It is further comprised on nine behavior factors:Independent Functioning, Economic Activity, Language Development, Physical Development, Prevocational, Numbers and Time, Responsibility, Vocational Activity, Socialization, and Self-Direction. Second Part of domains is designed to measureseven behaviors impairment: Social Behavior, Trustworthiness, Conformity Social Engagement, Stereotyped, Hyperactive Behavior, Self-Abusive Behavior andDisturbing Interpersonal Behavior.High scores on demonstrated higher prevalence of adaptive behavior and low scores expose lower higher prevalence of adaptive behavior.

RESULTS

Ms. XY's scores on the GARS-2 and ABS placed her in the Mild level of autism at her earlyappointment (seeTable 1). On the Colored progressive Matrices (CPM), it was administered on her butshe unable to perform to it because she was quite and just looked but showed no interest in the (CPM). On HTP test,she could not draw HTP because she was unable to respond to it. Based on both psychiatric assessment and formal testing, shehas been diagnosedin autism spectrum disorder.

The ABS percentile for Ms. XY on all 16 domains is reported in Table 2& 3. Study instruments results demonstrated that she was performed significantly poor on following domains: independent functioning, economic activity, numbers and time, self-direction, responsibility, socialization, stereotyped and hyperactive behavior, and social engagement. She also illustrated behavior impairments especially in areas of personal self-sufficiency, community self-sufficiency, personal-social responsibility, and social engagement, personal adjustment factors. Impairment ofthese domains and factors strongly recommended a diagnosisof autism spectrum disorder(Lambert, Nihira, & Leland, 1993).

Table 1 Diagnostic Data

T	e	s	t	s	R	a	w	s	c	o	r	e	s	/	p	e	r	c	e	n	t	i	l	e	R	a	n	g	e
G	A	R	S	-	2	3																			1	M	i	l	d
C		P		M		-																							
H			T		P	-																							

Table 2 ABS findings on domain

Serial No	Domains	Range
1	Independent Functioning	Below Average
2	Physical Development	Average
3	Economic Activity	Very Poor
4	Language Development	Average
5	Numbers and Time	Poor
6	Prevocational/vocational Activity	Average
7	Self-Direction	Poor
8	Responsibility	Below Average
9	Socialization	Poor
10	Social Behavior	Average
11	Conformity	Average
12	Trustworthiness	Average
13	Stereotyped and Hyperactive Behavior	Poor
14	Self-Abuse Behavior	Average
15	Social Engagement	Poor
16	Disturbing Interpersonal Behavior	Average

Table 3 ABS findings on factors

Serial No	Factors	Scores
1	Personal Self-Sufficiency	Below Average
2	Community Self-Sufficiency	Very Poor
3	Personal-Social responsibility	Very Poor
4	Social Engagement	Below Average
5	Personal adjustment	Poor

DISCUSSION

In this single case study, we inspected the implicit clinical case study of autism spectrum disorder at school age (6 years of age) in a young girl. We employed a combination of self-report inventories and projective technique to investigate autistic's the psychological and behavioral manifestation. Ms. XY reported progressive symptoms of autism spectrum disorder. She exhibited impairment in various behavior's domains for instance personal self-sufficiency, community self-sufficiency, and personal-social responsibility, and social engagement, personal adjustment on adaptive behavior scale (Lambert, Nihira, & Leland, 1993). These dysfunctional behavioral pattern indicated that she experienced significant emotional, social impairment, which is strongly suggested toward autism disorder (Tager-Flusberg, & Kasari, 2013; American Psychiatric Publishing, 2013).

Gallium Autism Rating Scale (GARS-2) illustrated that she had impairment in reciprocal social interactions, communication skills, restricted, repetitive, as well as stereotyped patterns of interests and behavior. GARS-2 results also revealed suggestive of autism disorder and complimentary to the results of the ABS (Lambert, Nihira, & Leland, 1993).

Treatment

Psychosocial Therapies

Several numerous psychosocial treatments were established tackling both the main symptoms and comorbid symptoms of autism spectrum disorder (ASD).

Applied Behavioral Analysis (ABA)

It is an intervention based on operant conditioning and learning's theories. It comprises particular treatment targets, joined with positive reinforcement (edible rewards or tokens, verbal praise), with learning-trials's repetition a key factor (Landa, 2007). It has been hypothesized that early, rigorous ABA treatment may guide to incredible consequences, including approximately half of the autistic children getting this intervention obtaining considerable IQ points and being mainstreamed into normal classes (Lovaas, 1987). Several previous studies lacked methodological comprehensive, and imitation with randomized controlled trials has been required to approve like claims. One planned previous meticulous applied behavior analysis (ABA) therapy model, the traditional Start Denver approach, demonstrated noteworthy adaptive behavior and cognitive gets over the period of two years in a randomized controlled trial in preschool-aged kids (Dawson et al., 2010). Previous study explained that children with autism exhibited higher language development, daily living skills acquisition, intellectual functioning, and social functioning, language improvement after receiving ABA intervention (Virués-Ortega, 2010). In this approach, a teacher sequentially

presents a discriminative stimulus (an instruction) and provides consequences for a correct or incorrect response. In the applied behavior analysis break the whole task in smaller pieces and give the one command to the child at a time. Applied behavior analysis is very helpful for the child who having autism because the these child has difficulty to follow the instruction in a row and they are unable to understand the different instruction at a time so through applied behavior analysis break the instruction into smaller pieces through this process the child is able to understand the instruction and through this process the child behavior can be modify(Hastings, 2003; Cooper, Heron, &Heward, 2007; Foxx, 2008;Virués-Ortega, 2010; Makrygianni, Gena, Katoudi, &Galanis, 2018; Morrier, & Ziegler, 2018).

Picture Exchange Communication System (PECS)

Picture exchange communication system is suggested for the client which enables the client to communicate using pictures that represent ideas, activities, or items. The client is able to convey requests, needs, and desires to others by simply handing them a picture(Tang &Winoto, 2018).

Play Therapy

Roughly consists of therapist playing with child while talking to the child and trying to induce the child to talk. The goal is to help the child acquire language and the working knowledge of everyday life we all require. The method is to use play, which is a component of a typical child's language acquisition, in conjunction with constant interaction with a therapist. Play therapy has been used for autistic children and children with emotional disturbances (Overley, Snow, Mossing, Degges-White, & Holmes, 2018; Hiles Howard, Lindaman, Copeland, & Cross, 2018).

Speech Therapy

Language deficits are one of the core aspects of autism, and speech therapy provides professional help and guidance in communication development for individuals with autism. Speech therapy involves much more than simply teaching a child to correctly pronounce words. The goal of speech therapy is to improve all aspects of communication. This includes: comprehension, expression, sound production, and social use of language. Speech therapy may include sign language and the use of picture symbols . At its best, a specific speech therapy program is tailored to the specific weaknesses and the environment of the individual child. Speech therapy should include four aspects:Speech therapy should begin early in a child's life and be frequent, Therapy should be rooted in practical experience in the child's life, Therapy should encourage spontaneous communication, Any communication skills learned during speech therapy should be generalizable to multiple situations (Namasivayam et al., 2018; Miniscalco, Fernell, Thompson, Sandberg, Kadesjö, &Gillberg, 2018)

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